

Ota-onalar agressiv xulq-atvorining farzand tarbiyasiga ta'siri
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Annotatsiya:

Mazkur maqolada ota-onalik psixologiyasi, ota-onalarning farzandga nisbatan munosabati haqida so'z boradi. Shuningdek ota-onalar agressiv xulq - atvorining farzand tarbiyasiga o'zaro ta'siri haqida ma'lumotlar beriladi.

Kalit so'zlar: ota -oanalik psixologiyasi, bola, shaxs, oilaviy muhit, avtoritar, agressiya, xulq -atvor, psixologik yondashuv, intizom, jismoniy.

Agressiv ota-ona bolani itoat qilish uchun nazorat qilish yoki bosim o'tkazish uchun tahdid yoki jazodan foydalanishni o'z ichiga oladi. Ota-onalarning bolalarga nisbatan tajovuzkorligi psixologik yoki jismoniy bo'lishi mumkin. Bu zaharli ota-onalar deb ham ataladi. Psixologik tajovuzkor ota-onalar o'z farzandlarini ularga bo'ysunish uchun og'zaki tahdid qilishadi. Bolalar tez-tez nomlanadi, haqoratlanadi, kamsitiladi, qasam ichadi va la'natlanadi.

Aybdorlik hissi, sevgidan voz kechish, shaxsiy hujumlar va og'zaki muloqotni cheklash kabi psixologik nazorat ota-onalarning tajovuzkorligining yana bir shaklidir. Ota-onalarning bu salbiy taktikasi bolalarning xatti-harakatlari va fikrlariga bosim o'tkazish va manipulyatsiya qilish uchun ishlatiladi.

Bu tajovuzkor ota-onalar farzandlarini to'g'ridan-to'g'ri urishmasa ham, ular ko'pincha tahdid qilishadi. Ba'zi hollarda ular o'z farzandlarini islohot maktablari kabi qo'rqinchli joylarga yuborish yoki uydan haydab yuborish bilan tahdid qilishadi. Jismoniy tajovuzkor ota-onalar o'z farzandlarini jismoniy kuch bilan jazolaydi yoki qo'rqitadi. Og'riq va qo'rquvni uyg'otish uchun ular bolalarini urishlari, urishlari, urishlari, chimchilashlari yoki silkitishlari mumkin.

Bunday tarbiyaning oqibatlarini ko'pincha bolaga zarar keltiradi. Ushbu tajovuzkor ota-ona uslubining salbiy ta'siridan biri shundaki, u bolalarning tajovuzkorligini rag'batlantiradi va bolalar farovonligiga zarar yetkazadi. Bunday bolalar zo'ravon bo'lishadi yoki zo'ravonlik qilish ehtimoli ko'proq bo'ladi.

Ota-onalarning qo'pol munosabati barcha yoshdagi bolalarga salbiy ta'sir qiladi, lekin juda yosh bolalar ayniqsa zaifdir, chunki ular o'z tajribasini boshqalar bilan solishtirish imkoniyati kam va ular nomaqbul xatti-harakatlarni o'rganishga moyil bo'ladi. Uyda jismonan yoki ruhiy qurbon bo'lgan bolalar bezori, zo'ravonlik qurboni yoki ikkalasiga aylanish ehtimoli oshgan.

Tadqiqotlar doimiy ravishda bolalar va o'smirlardagi majburlovli ota-onalik va antisosial va tajovuzkor xatti-harakatlar o'rtasidagi bog'liqlikni ko'rsatdi. Intizom, xususan, jazo intizomi bezorilik bilan bog'liq muhim omildir.

Agressiv ota-onalar, xususan, jismoniy tarbiya, bolalar va o'smirlarda tajovuz bilan bog'liq. Ota-onalarning tajovuzkor amaliyotlaridan foydalanadiganlar o'z farzandlariga jazo va dushmanlik xatti-harakatlari ular xohlagan narsaga erishishda samarali ekanligini o'rgatadi. Bolalar zo'ravonlik boshqalarga nisbatan o'zaro ta'sir qilish va nazorat qilishning qonuniy usuli ekanligiga ishonishlari mumkin, bu ularni bunday xatti-harakatlarga taqlid qilishga olib kelishi mumkin. Tengdoshlarning tajovuzkorligi ota-onalarning psixologik nazorati bilan ham bog'liq. Qo'rqitishdan tashqari, psixologik nazorat ham huquqbuzarlik, zo'ravonlik, xavfli xatti-harakatlar va bo'ysunmaslik kabi tashqi belgilar bilan bog'liq.

Bolalik va o'smirlik davridagi psixologik nazorat, shuningdek, bolaning yomon moslashuvi va o'smirlik va yoshlikdagi natijalar bilan bog'liq. Bolalar haqorat, manipulyatsiya va kamsitishni o'zaro ta'sir va nazorat qilish vositasi sifatida ishlatishni o'rganadilar. Uyda psixologik zo'ravonlikka uchragan bolalarda tashvish va o'zini past baholash hissi paydo bo'lishi mumkin, natijada ular o'zlarini tengdoshlaridan samarali himoya qila olmaydilar. Bunday bolalar zo'ravonlik qurboni rolini o'z zimmalariga olishlari mumkin.

Tadqiqotlar shuni ko'rsatdiki, ota-onalarning bolalik davridagi tajovuzkorligi bolalarning maktabda qayta qurbon bo'lish xavfini oshiradi. Bezori bolalar, shuningdek, ruhiy tushkunlik va tashvish kabi ruhiy kasalliklarga ko'proq moyil bo'ladi. Bolaligida jismonan intizomga ega bo'lgan dushman-tajovuzkor ota-ona ko'proq jirkanch va kamroq tarbiyalovchi tarbiya uslubini namoyon etadi.

Ota-onalarning kam samarali xatti-harakatlari va o'z farzandlariga nisbatan shunga o'xshash haqoratli xatti-harakatlarga ishonish va amalda qo'llash ehtimoli ko'proq bo'ladi. Ayniqsa, ota-onaning dushmanona xatti-harakatlari bilan o'sgan o'smirlar kelajakdagi farzandlariga nisbatan tajovuzkorlik bilan harakat qilishadi.

Avtoritar ota-ona tarbiyasi Baumrindning to'rtta tarbiya uslubidan biridir. Ota-onalarning bunday tarbiya uslubi sovuqqon, javobsiz va talabchan ota-onalar tomonidan tavsiflanadi. Ular qattiqqo'l, dushman, qarama-qarshilik va kelishmovchilik pozitsiyasini namoyon etadi.

Psixologik va jismoniy zo'ravonlik bilan tarbiyalash jamiyatdagi zo'ravonlikning intensivligi bilan ijobiy bog'liq. O'rtacha va yuqori darajadagi jamoat zo'ravonligiga duchor bo'lgan onalar jazolovchi ota-onadan ikki baravar ko'proq foydalanadi.

Turli sabablarga ko'ra, bolalar zo'ravonligi qurbonlari ko'pincha bir qator aybdorlik yoki sharmandalikni boshdan kechirishadi. Siz shunday his qilishingiz kerak bo'lgan odam emassiz. Bundan tashqari, boshqalar sizni tanqid qilishiga yoki o'zingizga shubha qilishiga yo'l qo'ymang. O'zingizni his qilish uchun hech kimning ruxsatiga muhtoj emassiz. Ota-onani zo'ravonlik bilan tarbiyalashni to'xtatish uchun ota-ona jazo intizomga javob emasligiga ishonishi kerak. Bolani kaltaklash yoki aybdor qilishdan tashqari, boshqa samaraliroq usullar mavjud.

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